

OPINIONS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHER GRADUATES ON PUBLIC PERSONNEL SELECTION EXAM

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Abstract:

Taking Personnel to Government departments via Public Personnel Selection Exam was first done in 1999. Ministry of Education used this exam results in any of the Teacher Assignments. In the year 2013, as it is thought that this exam was not sufficient for Teacher Selection, another exam which measures Teaching Field Knowledge for some branches was conducted. But the Physical Education graduates have to enter only the Public Personnel Selection Exam. This study is to find out the thoughts of the Physical Education graduates about the Public Personnel Selection Exam. In the research, The views of Physical Education Teacher graduates on Public Personnel Selection Exam, whether Teaching Field Knowledge questions should be asked or not, the views of teachers' on these assignment style, views on this job for their future, in which field they see themselves successful, what kind of problems they face while getting ready for this exam and what their advices are for this exam were tried to be answered. Open-ended questions were asked to the candidates in this research. Interview method, which is one of the qualitative methods, was used for 50 candidates who have graduated from different universities. At the end of the research it was found that most of the Physical Education teacher candidates were opposed to Public Personnel Selection Exam because it was not adequate to designate and assign the teachers, the preparing phase for the exam was creating anxiety and fear, the exam was creating a negative point of view about teaching profession and it was not able to contribute a lot to the profession. In addition, as a result it was reached that teacher candidates were expressing their ideas as there should be field information exams besides Public Personnel Selection Exam also for physical education teacher candidate's assignments like other branch teachers assignments.

Keywords: physical education, teacher candidate, public personnel selection exam

1. Introduction

In Education sector, the main factor is the teacher. Therefore, the capacity and the education level of the teacher are very important. It's the oldest and one of the most important jobs in the world. Therefore, the personality, the capacity and the views towards the teaching job is very important. (Sözer, 1996; Alım and Bekdemir, 2006) Habits and behaviours of teachers affect the students as well. (Varış, 1973) Therefore, their attitudes towards the teaching job affect their quality of teaching as well. (Erdem et al., 2005) Teacher assignments are different in every country. In Turkey, teachers are selected by Public Personnel Selection Exam which is organized by an institution called Student Selection and Placement Center. There is also a similar system in some countries such as Germany, Austria, France, Spain, and Luxembourg and in some states of United States. These exams are usually paper based but sometimes they may be orally in some countries such as Belgium, Greece, Netherlands and Portugal. (Semerci and Özer, 2006) As the number of graduated teachers is more than the teacher assignments, this exam has to be done compulsorily. Therefore, Public personnel Selection Exam are practised by Student Selection and Placement Center every year. (Doğan and Şahin, 2009) Assignments are done according to their exam scores and wishes by Personnel General Management Association (Ministry of Education, 2010).

When we look at the statistics, there are researches about this exam, anxieties of candidates, and views of teacher candidates in recent years. (Bahar, 2011; Baştürk, 2007; Çimen and Yılmaz, 2011; Döş and Sağır, 2012; Eraslan, 2004; Gündoğdu et al., 2008; Karaca, 2011; Karataş and Güleş, 2013; Nartgun, 2011; Sezgin and Duran, 2011; Toker Gökçe, 2012; Tösten et al., 2012; Yılmaz and Altinkurt, 2011) These researches are usually practised to those who are still in faculties or attending to the courses. Different datas from different groups are thought to help to find out different perspectives. Public Personnel Selection Exam is very important in the candidates' lives. In this study, we aim the views of candidates about this exam. The present situation of this exam on these candidates is the main objective of this study. Qualified education can be obtained by only qualified teachers. Therefore, teachers should believe themselves first and should be full educated and should have positive behaviours towards their jobs. In this study, the views of Physical Education Teaching graduates are tried to find out and the questions below are tried to be answered.

According to the Physical Education Teaching Graduates;

1. What are their general thoughts about Public Personnel Selection Exam?
2. Should Questions about their Field Knowledge asked or not? Why?
3. How should teacher candidates be assigned? Via Exam or not?
4. How does this exam affect their perspectives towards their jobs?

5. In which part of exam do they see themselves successful? General Cultural Knowledge, General ability or Educational Sciences?
6. Do they think that this exam will make a role in their jobs for the future?
7. What kind of problems do they face while getting prepared for this exam?
8. What are their expectations from this exam?
9. What are their advices for this exam?

2. Method

In the research, case study, which is one of the qualitative methods, was used. Qualitative methods are more flexible and offer different approaches than quantitative methods. (Gay et al, 2006)

Case study searches the case in its own life and situation frame and when there is more than one evidence. (Yin, 1984; Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2006)

2.1. Research Group

Different open-ended Questions were asked to 50 Physical Education Teaching Graduates from different universities in Gaziantep. These data about research are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Personal Characteristics of Research Group (N = 50)

Variables	Groups	n	%
Age	21	5	10
	22	14	28
	23	12	24
	24	10	20
	25	4	8
	26	2	4
	27	2	4
	28	1	2
Sex	Female	28	56
	Male	22	44
Number of Exam Experience	1	25	50
	2	12	24
	3	10	20
	4	3	6
Attendance to the Course	Yes	38	76
	No	12	24

N: 50

When we look at the Table 1, we see that there are some personal characteristics of the research group. When we look at their ages ; 5 (%10) 21 years old, 14 (%28) 22 years old, 12 (%24) 23 years old, 10 (%20) 24 years old, 4 (%8) 25 years old, 2 (%4) 26 years old, 2 (%4) 27 years old, and 1 teacher candidate %2 is 28 years old. When we look at the sexes, we see that; 28 (%56) are female, 22 (%44) are male. When we look at their Number of attendance, we see that; 25 (%50) have entered this exam for the first time. 12 (%24) have entered twice, 10 (%20) have entered three times, 3 (%6) have entered fourth times. When we look at their attendance to the courses, we see that; 38 (%76) are attending to the courses, 12 (%24) don't go to any courses to prepare for this exam.

2.2. Preparing Open-Ended Questions and Practising

To prepare the interview forms, 100 teacher candidates we asked to write a composition about their thoughts for Public Personnel Selection Exam. After checking out these compositions, the interview forms were drafted. One of the logical ways to test the measuring instrument is to refer to the expert opinion. (Büyüköztürk, 2006) After the experts checked and made the necessary regulations on the interview forms, 4 questions to determine the personality features and 9 open-ended questions were asked. These questions are below.

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4. How does this exam affect their perspectives towards their jobs?
5. In which part of exam do they see themselves successful? General Cultural Knowledge, General ability or Educational Sciences?
6. Do they think that this exam will make a role in their jobs for the future?
7. What kind of problems do they face while getting prepared for this exam?
8. What are their expectations from this exam?
9. What are their advices for this exam?

These interview forms were given to 50 teacher candidates who graduated from different universities. While practising these forms, the aims and importance were told to the candidates. At the end of the practise, the data were collected together and the similar answers were grouped under same themes.

3. Analysis of Data

The data obtained from the interview form were analyzed via content analysis method. Content analysis is used in qualitative researches when there are subthemes. (Yıldırım

and Şimşek, 2006) The data were saved separately and coded as groups. These groups and codes were presented to experts and then given the final shape and get ready for analysis. Themes were shaped and measured their frequencies and percentages and made charts from them. Descriptive analysis was used while making data analysis. Finally, reports were made and the findings were presented.

4. Findings and Comments

These are the findings of views of Physical Education Teacher Graduates on Public Personnel Selection Exam.

Table 2: Distribution of views about Public Personnel Selection Exam

Themes	n	%
Unnecessary Exam	16	31.4
Not very qualitative Exam	8	15.7
Not a very Systematic Exam	7	13.8
Necessary Exam	6	11.8
Study-based Exam	4	7.8
Difficult Exam	4	7.8
Annoying Exam for Teacher Candidates	2	3.9
Frightening Exam	2	3.9
Should be More Field-based	2	3.9
Total	51	100

In Table 2: We see that distribution of views about Public Personnel Selection Exam. There are 9 themes. We see that participants have views about more than one theme. When we look at the percentages, we see that %31.4 think that it is an unnecessary exam. %15.7 think that it is not a qualitative exam. %13.8 think that it is not a systematic exam. %11.8 think that it is a necessary exam. %7.8 think that they should study a lot to pass it. %7.8 think that it is a difficult exam. %7.8 think that it is an annoying exam. %3.9 think that it is a frightening exam. %3.9 think that it should be a more Field-based exam.

Table 3: The percentages of the opinions of the research group on content knowledge questions in Public Personnel Selection Exam

Themes	n	%
Yes, content knowledge questions should be asked.	31	62
No, content knowledge questions shouldn't be asked.	19	38
Total	50	100

In Table 3, the percentages of the opinions of the research group on content knowledge questions in Public Personnel Selection Exam are shown. Two opinions have been obtained about whether content knowledge questions should be asked in Public Personnel Selection Exam. Accordingly, 39 teacher candidates (%62) have stated that content questions should be asked in Public Personnel Selection Exam; on the other hand, 19 teacher candidates (%38) have stated that content questions shouldn't be asked in Public Personnel Selection Exam.

Table 4: The percentages of the opinions of the research group on how teacher candidates should be appointed as a teacher

Themes	N	%
They should be appointed as a teacher by examination.	31	50
They should be appointed as a teacher without examination.	15	24.2
They should be appointed as a teacher by content examination.	6	9.6
They should be appointed as a teacher by practice exams.	6	9.6
They should be appointed as a teacher only by interview.	3	4.9
They should be appointed as a teacher without any interview.	1	1.7
Total	62	100

In Table 4, the percentages of the opinions of the research group on how teacher candidates should be appointed as a teacher are shown. Six opinions have been obtained about how teacher candidates should be appointed as a teacher. The research group has stated more than one opinion. These themes are: 'They should be appointed as a teacher by examination.' (%50), 'They should be appointed as a teacher without examination.' (%24.2), 'They should be appointed as a teacher by content examination.' (%9.6), 'They should be appointed as a teacher by practice exams.' (%9.6), 'They should be appointed as a teacher only by interview.' (%4.9), 'They should be appointed as a teacher without any interview.' (%1.7).

Table 5: The percentages of the opinions of the research group on how Public Personnel Selection Exam affects their perspectives on teaching profession

Themes	N	%
It affected my perspective on teaching profession in a negative way.	28	53.8
It decreases the value of teaching profession.	8	15.4
It alienates teacher candidates from the profession.	7	13.5
It affected my perspective on teaching profession positively.	7	13.5
It hasn't changed my opinions.	2	3.8
Total	52	100

In Table 5, the percentages of the opinions of the research group on how Public Personnel Selection Exam affects their perspectives on teaching profession are shown. Five opinions on how Public Personnel Selection Exam affects teacher candidates' perspectives on teaching profession have been obtained. These themes are: 'It affected my perspective on teaching profession in a negative way.' (%53.8), 'It decreases the value of teaching profession.' (%15.4), 'It alienates teacher candidates from the profession.' (%13.5), 'It affected my perspective on teaching profession positively.' (%13.5), 'It hasn't changed my opinions.' (%3.8).

Table 6: The percentages of the opinions of the research group on which part of the test they see themselves they are most proficient in

Themes	N	%
Educational Sciences	29	48.4
General Knowledge	13	21.7
General Ability	12	20
Proficient in all parts	4	6.6
Unsatisfactory in all parts	2	3.3
Total	60	100

In Table 6, the percentages of the opinions of the research group on which part of the test they see themselves they are most proficient in are shown. Five opinions on which part of the test the research group see themselves they are most proficient in have been obtained. The research group has stated more than one opinion. These themes are: 'Educational Sciences' (%48.4), 'General Knowledge' (%21.7), 'General Ability' (%20), 'Proficient in all parts' (%6.6), 'Unsatisfactory in all parts' (%3.3).

Table 7: The percentages of the opinions of the research group on the contribution of Public Personnel Selection Exam on teaching profession

Themes	N	%
No, it will not make any contribution.	34	63
Yes, it will make a big contribution.	13	24
It will make a contribution to a certain degree.	7	13
Total	54	100

In Table 7, the percentages of the opinions of the research group on the contribution of Public Personnel Selection Exam on teaching profession are shown. Three opinions of the research group on the contribution of Public Personnel Selection Exam on teaching profession have been obtained. These themes are: 'No, it will not make any

contribution.’ (%63), ‘Yes, it will make a big contribution.’ (%24), ‘It will make a contribution to a certain degree.’ (%13).

Table 8: The percentages of the opinions of the research group on the problems they encountered while preparing for the Public Personnel Selection Exam

Themes	N	%
I had psychological problems.	19	34.5
The time given to prepare for the exam is not enough.	12	21.8
I can't study systematically.	8	14.5
I have lack of motivation.	5	9.1
The questions are very hard.	4	7.3
I had financial problems.	4	7.3
I didn't have any problems.	3	5.5
Total	55	100

In Table 8, the percentages of the opinions of the research group on the problems they encountered while preparing for the Public Personnel Selection Exam are shown. Seven opinions of the research group on the problems they encountered while preparing for the Public Personnel Selection Exam have been obtained. The research group has stated more than one opinion. These themes are: ‘I had psychological problems.’ (%34.5), ‘The time given to prepare for the exam is not enough.’ (%21.8), ‘I can't study systematically.’ (%14.5), ‘I have lack of motivation.’ (%9.1), ‘The questions are very hard.’ (%7.3), ‘I had financial problems.’ (%7.3), ‘I didn't have any problems.’ (%5.5).

Table 9: The percentages of the opinions of the research group on what they expect from Public Personnel Selection Exam

Themes	N	%
I want to be appointed as a teacher.	25	45.5
I don't have any expectation.	13	23.7
The exam must be fair and reliable.	5	9.1
There should be no exam.	4	7.2
The exam system should be changed.	3	5.5
It should be knowledge-based exam.	2	3.6
The exam is efficient enough to test our knowledge.	2	3.6
The questions should be easier.	1	1.8
Total	55	100

In Table 9, the percentages of the opinions of the research group on what they expect from Public Personnel Selection Exam are shown. Eight opinions of the research group on what they expect from Public Personnel Selection Exam have been obtained. The

research group has stated more than one opinion. These themes are: 'I want to be appointed as a teacher.' (%45.5), 'I don't have any expectation.' (%23.7), 'The exam must be fair and reliable.' (%9.1), 'There should be no exam.' (%7.2), 'The exam system should be changed.' (%5.5), 'It should be knowledge-based exam.' (%3.6), 'The exam is efficient enough to test our knowledge.' (%3.6), 'The questions should be easier.' (%1.8).

Table 10: The percentages of the opinions of the research group on their recommendations for Public Personnel Selection Exam

Themes	n	%
There should be no exam.	19	37.3
Questions should only be based on our majors.	11	21.6
The exam system should be changed.	7	13.8
There should be no interviews.	6	11.8
The exam must be fair and reliable.	5	9.8
The exams should be easier.	1	1.9
There should be no questions about current events.	1	1.9
Exams should be interview-based.	1	1.9
Total	51	100

In Table 10, the percentages of the opinions of the research group on their recommendations for Public Personnel Selection Exam are shown. Eight opinions of the research group on their recommendations for Public Personnel Selection Exam have been obtained. The research group has stated more than one opinion. These themes are: 'There should be no exam.' (%37,3), 'Questions should be based on our majors.' (%21.6), 'The exam system should be changed.' (%13.8), 'There should be no interview.' (%11.8), 'The exam must be fair and reliable.' (%9.8), 'The exams should be easier.' (%1.9), 'There should be no questions about current events.' (%1.9), 'Exams should be interview-based.' (%1.9).

5. Conclusion, Recommendations, and Discussion

In this part of the research, I want to talk about the information that I obtained during the interviews I made with physical education teacher candidates.

When we have a look at the opinions of the research group on Public Personnel Selection Exam, we can easily see that the majority of them think this exam is not efficient enough to test our knowledge, and its system should be changed. Furthermore, the research group believes that Public Personnel Selection Exam is required, hard, and creates anxiety and fear among teacher candidates. Considering this fact, the efficiency of holding such an examination to assign candidates as teachers is a matter of debate,

and it can be said that this exam is a must to assign candidates as teachers for the first time. We can also say that it creates fear and anxiety among teacher candidates. In a study conducted by Tösten et al, (2012) in order to learn the opinions of teachers on Public Personnel Selection Exam it was conducted that teachers think this exam is not capable of choosing the right candidates in keeping with the principles of Ministry of National Education. On the other hand, in a study conducted by (Şimşek and Akgün, 2014) on the views of Social Studies teacher candidates about the field information part (ÖABS) in Public Personnel Selection Exam they concluded that Public Personnel Selection Exam alone is not enough to assign candidates as teachers for the first time. The study conducted by Semerci and Özer (2005) found out that teacher candidates doesn't think Public Personnel Selection Exam is fair and required. Therefore, both of these studies have a lot in common with our findings.

The majority of the research group (%62) expressed that Public Personnel Selection Exam should be the main exam to assign physical education teachers for the first time. On the other hand, the rest of the teacher candidates (%38) stated that field information part in Public Personnel Selection Exam should be omitted. Considering this fact, we can say that physical education teachers must also take field information exams. In a research conveyed by EBSAM (2011), majority of teacher candidates (%82) stated that field information questions must determine whether they will be teachers or not. This research supports our findings.

While the majority of the research group stated that teachers should be assigned via an exam; some teacher candidates think that teachers should be assigned without an exam, only via an exam to test their field information, via a practice exam, via job-related interview questions, or without any interviews. Considering these opinions of the research group, physical education teachers must also take field information exams (like other teacher candidates do), and Public Personnel Selection Exam must be fair to everyone. In a research done by (Şimşek and Akgün, 2014) the views that Public Personnel Selection Exam creates mentally depressed teacher candidates, compels teachers to memorize every single piece of information, demands great performance from candidates, does not have the quality to choose the right candidates to become teachers, and is not fair to everyone came into existence. The results of this research support our findings.

In the interviews with the members of the research group, 28 teacher candidates stated that their thoughts about teaching profession had changed in a negative way because of Public Personnel Selection Exam. Furthermore, the research group stated that this exam decreases the value of teaching profession. On the other hand, 7 teacher candidates stated that Public Personnel Selection Exam had changed their views about teaching profession in a positive way. Preparation process for the Public Personnel

Selection Exam creates anxiety among teacher candidates because they fear that they may not be able to be assigned as teachers after studying for four years in a university. Sezgin and Duran (2011) did a scientific study to find out teacher candidates' views about Public Personnel Selection Exam, to compare the content of Public Personnel Selection Exam and teacher candidates' course contents, and how it affects teacher candidates' views about teaching profession and their social lives. They used qualitative research methods in this study and concluded that teacher candidates don't think Public Personnel Selection Exam has the quality to choose qualified teachers for teaching profession. As is seen, we also reached similar results in our research.

When asked about which part the research group members see themselves most successful, 29 teacher candidates stated that they are best at social sciences part, 13 teacher candidates at general knowledge part, and 12 teacher candidates at general ability part. Additionally, 4 teacher candidates stated that they are successful in all parts, and 2 teacher candidates stated they are not successful in any part. Considering all these, we can say that physical education teachers are more successful in educational sciences.

When asked about the contribution of Public Personnel Selection Exam to teaching profession, majority of the research group stated that it will not make any contribution at all. However, a few teacher candidates stated Public Personnel Selection Exam will make a big or partial contribution to teaching profession. As a matter of course, we can say that Public Personnel Selection Exam will not make any contribution to teaching profession.

When asked about the problems the research group encountered while preparing for Public Personnel Selection Exam, they stated: 'I had psychological problems.', 'The time given to prepare for the exam is not enough.', 'I can't study systematically.', and 'I have lack of motivation.' From this fact, we can say that teacher candidates encounter many problems while preparing for Public Personnel Selection Exam. According to the study by Gündoğdu et al., (2008) teacher candidates got mentally tired, didn't have any time for a social activity, and had problems about making plans for the future. In addition to that, according to the study to find out teacher candidates' opinions on Public Personnel Selection Exam by (Baştürk 2007; Çimen and Yılmaz, 2011; Eraslan, 2006; Karaca, 2011; Sezgin and Duran, 2011). Karaca (2011), it was observed that teacher candidates have a negative attitude towards Public Personnel Selection Exam. In the study, it was emphasized that the exam creates anxiety, and stress among the candidates because it is the only exam they have to take to become a teacher, and that it is not qualitative enough to choose the correct teacher candidates. The results of this research support our findings.

When asked about what they expect from Public Personnel Selection Exam, majority of the research group stated that they want to be appointed as teachers. Furthermore, some of them stated that the exam must be fair and reliable, there should be no exam, the exam system should be changed, and it should be knowledge-based exam. From these points of views, we can say that teacher candidates just want to be appointed as teachers. In a study by Ensari and Deniz (1992) to find out Faculty of Education students' job-related expectations, majority of the students told that they believed they could find a job in their fields after they graduate. Considering these, anxiety and stress teacher candidates feel while preparing for Public Personnel Selection Exam have a negative effect on their attitude towards teaching profession. The results of these researches support our findings.

When asked about the opinions of the research group on their recommendations for Public Personnel Selection Exam, majority of the participants stated that there should be no exam; questions should only be based on our majors; the exam system should be changed; and there should be no interviews. Furthermore, the other teacher candidates who participated in the study stated that the exam must be fair and reliable; the exams should be easier; there should be no questions about current events. In a study by Karaca (2011) to find out teacher candidates' attitudes towards Public Personnel Selection Exam, it was found out that generally teacher candidates maintain a negative attitude towards Public Personnel Selection Exam. Moreover, in a study by Gürol and Sevindik (2009) it was observed that majority of teacher candidates think field information questions should be asked in Public Personnel Selection Exams. The results of these researches support our findings.

As a result, it was found out that majority of physical education teacher candidates are against Public Personnel Selection Exam because it is not sufficient enough to attain candidates as teachers, creates anxiety and fear among teacher candidates, has a negative effect on teaching profession, and will not play an important role for teacher candidates to become better teachers. Moreover, they stated that as in other teacher candidates' exams, there should also be a field information exam for physical education teacher candidates, too.

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